

Amorphous calcium phosphate nanoparticles for development of 3D printing bio-inks for orthopaedic application

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INTRODUCTION: 3D printing can be used to mimic structure of bone tissue for various needs of orthopaedics in laboratory conditions. For synthetic bone tissue, bio-ink would consist of inorganic and organic components, and cell containing media. Amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) was selected for this study as a prospective inorganic filler of the bio-inks because it is precursor of the biological apatite found in bone [1]. Aim of the study was to develop synthesis method of novel ACP nanoparticles with biomimetic bone-like chemical composition and characterize physicochemical properties thereof.

METHODS: Synthesis of biomimetic ACP (bio-ACP) was based on our previous work [2], where rapid precipitation of ACP was induced by increase of pH to 10-11 in a solution containing both Ca²⁺ and PO₄³⁻ ions. Here, water soluble salts containing the biomimetic ions (CO₃²⁻, Mg²⁺, Sr²⁺, Zn²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻) were added as well. Concentration of the ions was chosen as in the inorganic part of the bone. Precipitates of bio-ACP and ACP (n=3) were dried at 80-90 °C for 40-60 min. Characterization was done using XRD, FT-IR, SEM-EDS and specific surface area (SSA) and calculated particle size d_{BET} was determined using N₂ sorption system.

RESULTS: The modified synthesis produced bio-ACP, that was enriched with biomimetic ions. The amorphous state of the bio-ACP was confirmed with XRD. Further analysis of FT-IR spectra confirmed the well-known hydrated nature of ACP, furthermore the bio-ACP was carbonated. Using SEM-EDS analysis presence of the biomimetic ions was confirmed. SSA and d_{BET} of the bio-ACP nanoparticles was 86±10 m²/g and 25±3 nm. For comparison SSA and d_{BET} of ACP without biomimetic ions was 133±25 m²/g and 16±3 nm, respectively [2].

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS: Modification of synthesis process of calcium

phosphates may bring differences in terms of their physicochemical properties and later to response *in vitro*. Here, introduction of several water-soluble salts to the synthesis process of the ACP resulted in decrease of the values of SSA and particle size d_{BET}. However, there was no change in XRD patterns for ACP and bio-ACP as expected because most of the added ions stabilize amorphous phase. The presence of carbonate ions was detected by FT-IR. The carbonate ions are desirable structural feature as the biological calcium phosphate is carbonated as well. Assessment by SEM-EDS confirmed inclusion of the biomimetic ions within bio-ACP. However, exact location (integrated within the structure of ACP or adsorbed onto the surface of ACP) of the biomimetic ions could not be determined by using the current set of analysis techniques.

Overall, bio-ACP is a promising filler of 3D printing bio-inks for orthopaedic application because it mimics physicochemical properties of the bone's inorganic component. Combination of biomimetic ACP with a suitable polymer matrix (e.g., GelMA or hyaluronic acid), and cells would produce bio-ink resembling composition of the bone tissue, as it is important for production of 3D printed scaffolds and organs on a chip for the orthopaedic application.

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